

APPENDIX A: Interview Guide

Background

1. Could you tell me a bit about yourself?
 - a. Age
 - b. Education
2. What experience do you have in the field?

Theme: Team

3. Can you describe how your software development team is composed and your role in the group?
4. What characteristics, values, and norms do you see your software development team sharing?
5. How would you describe the typical member?
6. Are there any specific qualities, skills, or values that you believe are necessary to be successful in your current software development team?
7. Do you see a match between your strengths and skills and the expectations, values, and norms in your software development team?
8. Have you experienced any advantages or challenges in having similar characteristics, values, and norms among the group members in the software development team?
9. Do you think it is important for team members to share characteristics, values, and norms in a software development team to achieve collaboration and high performance?

Theme: Leadership

10. Could you share a situation where a software development team member has shown leadership and contributed to the team's success?
11. Could you share a situation where another software development team member has shown leadership and inspired or motivated you?
12. Can you describe what qualities or characteristics you believe are most important for a leader in a software development team when it comes to creating a positive work environment and contributing to the team's success?
13. What are the advantages and disadvantages of having a leader who is also part of the software development team in terms of understanding the team's needs and vision?
14. What are the advantages and disadvantages of having a leader who is also part of the software development team versus an external leader?
15. How do you think your performance and motivation would be influenced by a leader you identify with?
16. Could you describe your thoughts on whether a typical team member would be more effective in a leadership role?

Conclusion

17. Is there anything else you would like to add?